

SALICYLAMIDOXIME AS AN ANALYTICAL REAGENT. PART I. REACTIONS OF SALICYLAMIDOXIME WITH METALLIC IONS

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The reactions of salicylamidoxime with various metallic ions have been fully investigated. It has been found that this substance behaves very much like the aldoxime with respect to the colour, solubility, etc. of its metallic derivatives; but the p_H of incipient precipitations of the metallic ions are somewhat higher in case of the amidoxime. Both these substances have been found to produce orange-yellow precipitates with titanium^{IV} in acid solution, although Flagg and Furman failed to observe any such reaction in their investigation on salicylaldoxime.

Copper (light green), nickel (greyish violet) and palladium (light yellow) compounds after drying at 110° have got the composition $(C_7H_7O_2N_2)_2 M$ (where $M = Cu, Ni, Pd$). The nickel and palladium compounds have been found to be diamagnetic, as is to be expected for dsp^2 square-planar complexes of these divalent metals. The copper compound is paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 1.81$).

The identification limits for Cu, Ni and Bi. by precipitation and that of Fe^{III} and U^{VI} by the formation of soluble colours in alkaline solution have been determined. Ti^{IV} and V^V afford coloured precipitates in acid solution, which are soluble in isoamyl alcohol. This has been made use of in the detection of these metals.

The reactions of *o*-hydroxybenzamidoxime or salicylamidoxime with various metallic ions have been fully investigated in an effort to find the possibility of using this substance as an analytical reagent. This substance, as also the compound salicylhydroxamic acid, contains the same copper specific group of *o*-hydroxy-arylaloximes, e.g., salicylaldoxime, as will be evident from the following representations of the three substances:

(Salicylaldoxime)

⇕

(Salicylhydroxamic acid)

⇕

(Salicylamidoxime)

Salicylaldoxime was first employed by Ephraim (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 1928 ; 1931, 64, 1210, 1215) for the detection and gravimetric determination of copper. Later on Flagg and Furman (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1940, 12, 529) studied the reactions of this substance, as also of its 5-chloro, 3:5-dibromo and 5-nitro derivatives, with various metallic ions. Since then several reports have appeared on the use of salicylaldoxime for the separation and determination of metals (Welcher, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Vol. III, pp. 259-71, D. Van Nostrand Co., Inc., 1947).

In recent years several reports have also appeared on the analytical reactions and applications of salicylhydroxamic acid (Musante, *Gazzetta*, 1948, 78, 536 ; Bhaduri and Ray, *Science & Culture*, 1952, 18, 95). It might therefore be interesting to investigate the reactions of salicylamidoxime as well, which is related to the two compounds referred to above. The results of such an investigation will naturally show the influence of a substituent $-NH_2$ group in place of the hydrogen atom, in the open-chain carbon atom of the aldoxime or of a corresponding $-OH$ group in salicylhydroxamic acid. Incidentally, it might be pointed out that the $-OH$ and $-NH_2$ groups are isoelectronic, but the former is acidic while the latter is basic in character in the particular cases concerned. Hence, a comparison of the reactions of the two substances might be suggestive of the influence of a basic constituent in place of an acidic one of the same electronic configuration. Furthermore, salicylamidoxime might be expected to offer some practical advantage over the aldoxime or the hydroxamic acid as a reagent, particularly because of its greater stability compared to that of the aldoxime and its solubility in acids and alkalis in which the reagent solution can be prepared (cf. Spilker, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2773 ; vide, properties of salicylamidoxime in the "Experimental").

An account of the general reactions of salicylamidoxime with various metallic ions is given in a following section. If these are compared with the results of Flagg and Furman (*loc. cit.*) for salicylaldoxime, it will be found that the amidoxime resembles the aldoxime, in its general behaviour, with respect to the colour, solubility, etc., of its metallic derivatives, but the pH s of incipient precipitation of metals with the amidoxime are somewhat higher. Furthermore, the amidoxime is much less sensitive than the aldoxime for the detection of vanadium. Although Flagg and Furman (*loc. cit.*) report that salicylaldoxime does not give any positive reaction with titanium, it has been found, however, that both the amidoxime and the aldoxime produce orange-yellow precipitates with Ti^{IV} in acid solution, which are soluble in organic solvents like chloroform and isoamyl alcohol.

Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} compounds of salicylamidoxime were prepared as usual by precipitation ; after washing and drying at 110° their compositions were found to correspond to $(C_7H_7O_2N_2)_2M$ (where $M = Cu, Ni, Pd$). From the known constitution of the metal-salicylaldoxime compounds (Feigl and Bondi, *Ber.*, 1931, 64, 2819 ; Cox, Pinkard, Wardlaw and Webster, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 459, 1455), the metal-salicylamidoximes may be represented by the following structure :

The solubility of these compounds in strong alkali solutions may be due to salt formation by the :NOH group, whereby the non-electrolytic complexes are converted into complex anions (cf. Feigl and Suter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 378; Thilo and Friedrich, *Ber.*, 1929, 62, 2998).

The nickel and palladium compounds have been found to be diamagnetic, which supports a square-planar structure of the dsp^2 bond-type. The copper compound is paramagnetic as usual.

Precipitation of copper, nickel, titanium and bismuth from aqueous solution by excess of salicylamidoxime affords a convenient method of detecting these metals. The identification limits, which are rather low, have been determined.

U^{VI} and Fe^{III} produce yellow and orange-red colour respectively with excess of the amidoxime in alkaline solution. Ti^{IV} and V^{V} produce orange-yellow and black precipitates respectively in acid solution, which can be extracted into *isoamyl* alcohol producing yellow and pink coloured layers. These have been made use of for the colorimetric detection (visual) of these metals.

EXPERIMENTAL

Salicylamidoxime (cf. Spilker, *loc. cit.*) was prepared by heating together salicylnitrile, hydroxylamine hydrochloride and Na_2CO_3 in aqueous-alcoholic solution for 4 to 5 hours at 90° in a pressure bottle. The mixture was then acidified with HCl and most of the alcohol distilled off on the water-bath. The residue was then cooled and treated with HCl to 1 *N* and repeatedly extracted with ether to remove the impurities. From the aqueous solution the amidoxime was precipitated by adding sodium bicarbonate. This was then recovered by extracting with ether and removing the ether in vacuo. The product was purified by crystallisation from hot water, after decolorising with active charcoal, and finally by dissolving in hot benzene and precipitating it with petroleum ether (boiling range $40^\circ\text{--}60^\circ$). The pure product gave fine white needle-shaped crystals, m. p. $97\text{--}98^\circ$.

The substance is easily soluble in alcohol, ether, chloroform, benzene, etc., but is insoluble in petroleum ether. It is only slightly soluble in cold water, but is more or less easily soluble in hot water. Dilute solutions of mineral acids and alkalis dissolve it readily. In aqueous or dilute hydrochloric acid solutions it remains unchanged even on boiling. The solid after melting remains unchanged even at 125° .

p_n-limits for the Precipitation of Metals

A fairly concentrated (1 *N* approx.) solution of alkali (NaOH) was added with stirring to 200 c.c. of a 0.001*M* solution of the metal-ion containing sufficient free acid and about 20% excess of the equivalent quantity of salicylamidoxime till a turbidity just appeared. The *p_n* of the solution at this point was determined with the help of a *p_n*-meter (Cambridge, bench type) and this gave the *p_n* of incipient precipitation of the metal-ion under the prescribed conditions. From this point onward the addition of alkali was continued and the *p_n* of the filtered solution was ascertained at intervals, and the metal-ion was tested for in the filtrates. The *p_n* just corresponding to the complete precipitation was thus obtained. These *p_n*-limits are recorded along with the general reactions of the amidoxime in Table I.

TABLE I

Reactions of salicylamidoxime with metallic ions.

Metal-ion.	Nature of reaction.	<i>p_n</i> of incipient pptn. in 0.001 <i>M</i> soln. of metallic ion.	Remarks.
Ag ⁺	Light yellow precipitate in neutral soln.	...	Precipitate soluble in acids and ammonia; solution in latter deposits silver as a mirror. Caustic alkalies convert the precipitate immediately into black metallic silver.
Pb ²⁺	White ppt.	6.6	Precipitate soluble in caustic soda.
Hg ²⁺	Light yellow ppt.	6.4	Precipitate decomposed by ammonia.
Cu ²⁺	Light green ppt.	3.2	Precipitate is soluble in ammonia and caustic soda. Precipitation is complete at and above <i>p_n</i> 3.9 (at least up to 6.5 <i>p_n</i>) in 0.001 <i>M</i> soln. of copper ion. Precipitate slightly soluble in solutions of alkali acetates, tartrates, ammonium chloride, but precipitation complete even in their presence if excess of reagent is used. It is completely insoluble in hot water and not decomposed by it.
Cd ²⁺	White crystalline ppt.	8.2	Precipitate is soluble in ammonia, and no precipitation occurs in presence of NH ₄ Cl.
B ³⁺	Yellow ppt. in caustic alkali soln.	<i>p_n</i> 9 approx.	Precipitate is stable to excess of NaOH.
Zn ²⁺	White crystalline ppt. in alkaline soln.	7.2	It is soluble in NaOH and also NH ₄ OH; NH ₄ Cl prevents precipitation.

TABLE I (contd.)

Metal-ion.	Nature of reaction.	pH of incipient pptn in 0.001 M soln of metallic ion.	Remarks.
Mn^{2+}	Dirty green ppt. in alkaline medium.	8.7	A greenish colour first appears at 7.2 pH . Precipitate is soluble in NaOH and also in NH_4OH . Precipitation occurs even in presence of NH_4Cl ; the addition of $H_2O_2-NH_4OH$ causes instantaneous precipitation.
Co^{2+}	Brown ppt. even in presence of NH_4Cl .	6.9	It is soluble in NH_4OH and in NaOH solutions.
Ni^{2+}	Light green ppt. in the cold and greyish violet in warm soln.	5.6	The colour of the green precipitate changes to greyish violet slowly on standing, but rapidly on warming. Precipitation is complete at and above pH 6.7 in 0.001 M solution of nickel ion, and at least up to pH 8. It is soluble in aqueous solutions of ammonia and of NH_4Cl . Even in presence of NH_4Cl complete precipitation occurs if the reagent be in excess.
Pd^{2+}	Yellow ppt. in acid soln. in presence of NaCl.	1.0 (approx.)	Precipitate is soluble in ammonia and NaOH solutions.
Fe^{2+}	In presence of a reducing agent like NH_3OH , HCl or H_2SO_3 , to prevent aerial oxidation, a brown ppt. is obtained.	5.5-6.0	It is soluble in NaOH and ammonia solutions forming red colour.
Fe^{3+}	Red-violet colour at 3.5-4.0 pH and orange-red above pH 6.	...	Light orange colour persists even up to 11 pH . In concentrated solutions of Fe^{3+} ion a red-brown precipitate appears at 5.5-6.0 pH which dissolves in NaOH giving an orange-red solution. Colour is bleached by F^- , PO_4^{3-} and $C_2O_4^{2-}$ ions. The soluble coloured products cannot be extracted into organic solvents, although the precipitate is soluble in isoamyl alcohol giving a dark red solution.
UO_2^{2+}	Orange-coloured ppt.	4.6	The precipitate is soluble in alkalis, as also in isoamyl alcohol giving yellow solutions. The coloured species formed in alkaline solution cannot be extracted into organic solvents.
Ti^{4+}	Deep yellow ppt. in acid (H_2SO_4) soln.	3.1	In warm solution precipitation is complete even at 3.2 pH , but colour of the precipitate is of maximum intensity at 3.6-6.8 pH . The precipitate is soluble in isoamyl alcohol giving a yellow solution in the solvent. The ppt. is decomposed by alkalis.

TABLE I (contd.)

Metal-ion.	Nature of reaction.	p_n of incipient pptn. in 0.001M soln of metallic ion.	Remarks.
VO_3^-	Greenish black ppt. in acid (H_2SO_4) soln.	2.3	The precipitate is soluble in isoamyl alcohol, giving a red-violet solution, but is insoluble in chloroform.
MoO_4^{2-}	Bright yellow colour in slightly acid soln.	~6	The colour is discharged by alkali and excess acid

Copper^{II}-salicylamidoxime.—A warm solution of cupric chloride (A. C. S., Merck & Co.), acidified with HCl, was treated with an excess of a little over twice the molar proportion of the amidoxime in 0.1 N-HCl, and to this mixture dilute alkali was gradually added to adjust the p_n of the solution to about 4.0-4.5 (tested by B. D. H. indicator paper). The mixture was set aside on the water-bath for about 10 minutes, after which the light green precipitate of the copper compound was filtered. The precipitate was then thoroughly washed with hot water and finally dried to a constant weight at 110°. [Found: N, 15.28; Cu, 17.37. Calc. for Cu ($C_7H_7O_2N_2$)₂: N, 15.32; Cu, 17.40 per cent].

The substance is light green in colour. It is insoluble in water, but soluble in acids, caustic alkalis and ammonia solutions. It is also somewhat soluble in a hot concentrated solution of sodium acetate or of ammonium chloride. The substance is paramagnetic: $\chi_g = 3.806 \times 10^{-5}$; $\chi_m = 1336.14 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_n = 1.81$.

Nickel^{II}-salicylamidoxime.—An acidified warm solution of nickel chloride (A. C. S., Merck & Co.) was treated with a little more than twice the molar proportion of the pure amidoxime, dissolved in 0.1 N-HCl, and to this mixture dilute ammonia was gradually added to adjust the p_n of the solution to about 7.0-7.5 (tested by B. D. H. indicator paper). The precipitated nickel compound is initially light green in colour, especially if the precipitation starts at not too high a temperature, but readily changes to greyish violet on warming. The mixture was kept on the water-bath for about 10 to 15 minutes and then the precipitated nickel compound was filtered, washed thoroughly with hot water containing a little amount of ammonia (to adjust its p_n to near about 7), and finally dried for one hour to a constant weight at 110°. [Found: N, 15.46; Ni, 16.21. Calc. for Ni ($C_7H_7O_2N_2$)₂: N, 15.52; Ni, 16.28 per cent].

The substance is greyish violet in colour. It is insoluble in water but soluble in acids, alkalis and ammonia solutions. The compound is diamagnetic: $\chi_g = -0.6521 \times 10^{-5}$; $\chi_m = -235.2 \times 10^{-6}$.

Palladium^{II}-salicylamidoxime.—A warm acidified solution of palladous chloride in aqueous sodium chloride was treated with a little over twice the molar proportion of the amidoxime, dissolved in 0.1N-HCl, and the p_n was adjusted to 2.5-3.0 by adding KOH solution. The palladium compound was precipitated as a light yellow floppy mass. This was set aside at room temperature for a few minutes, then filtered and the precipitated compound washed thoroughly with hot water and dried at 110°. [Found: N, 13.61; Pd, 26.02. Calc. for Pd ($C_7H_7O_2N_2$)₂: N, 13.70; Pd, 26.10 per cent]. It is a light yellow powder which is soluble in acids, alkalis and ammonia solutions. The substance is diamagnetic.

Identification Limits of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Bi^{III} and Ti^{IV} by Precipitation with Salicylamidoxime

A definite volume of the solution of the metal-ion of varying concentrations was treated with an excess of the concentrated amidoxime solution, and the p_H of the resulting mixture was adjusted thereafter, if necessary, by adding acid or alkali as required, for the appearance of any opalescence of the following colours :

Copper ...	greenish white	Bismuth ...	yellowish white
Nickel ...	greyish white	Titanium ...	Do

The smallest amount of the metal required to produce an observable turbidity in each case was determined in this manner. The results are shown below.

TABLE II

Metal ion.	* Identification limit.	Concentration limit.
Cu ²⁺	1.00 γ (1 c. c.)	1 : 10 ⁶
Ni ²⁺	0.60 γ (1 c. c.)	1 : 1.66 $\times 10^6$
Bi ³⁺	20.00 γ (3 c. c.)	1 : 1.50 $\times 10^5$
Ti ⁴⁺	0.53 γ (0.1 c. c.)	1 : 1.89 $\times 10^5$

* Feigl, *mikrochem.*, 1923, 1, 4.

† Hahn, *ibid*, 1930, 8, 75.

Detection of U^{VI}, Fe^{III}, Ti^{IV} and V^V by Colour-formation with Salicylamidoxime

Fe^{III}.—0.005 *M* aqueous solution of salicylamidoxime (5 c. c.) of p_H 9.0-9.5 (adjusted by adding KOH) when treated with 0.1 c. c. of 0.0005 *M* solution of Fe³⁺ (ferric nitrate) was found to be just distinguishable from a blank, prepared identically, but without adding the iron solution. Thus, 2.8 γ Fe has been detected. Observations were made lengthwise through the columns of solutions contained in visual colorimeter tubes of 0.45 cm² cross-section. The p_H of the solution after the addition of the iron solution should be within the range of 8.3-10.0, which is the optimum p_H range for the colour formation. This has been found out separately.

U^{VI}.—An aqueous solution of salicylamidoxime (0.005 *M*, 5 c. c.) with as little as 0.2 c. c. of 0.005 *M*-UO₂(NO₃)₂ at a p_H of 7.9-9.2 produces a yellow colour just distinguishable from the blank; 23.8 γ uranium has thus been detected. Observations were made as in the case of the detection of iron.

Ti^{IV}.—The optimum p_H for the extraction of the yellow precipitate obtained in acid solution has been found to be 3.6-6.8. As little as 2.95 γ Ti can be detected by extracting with 1 c. c. of *isoamyl* alcohol from 15 c. c. of a solution of 0.01 *M* in salicylamidoxime and at 4-5 p_H . Observations were made in colorimeter tubes of 0.75 cm² cross-section.

V^V.—From an acid (H₂SO₄) solution of vanadic acid, at a p_H of 3-4, vanadium is incompletely precipitated. The pink colour formed by the greenish black precipitate on dissolving in *isoamyl* alcohol can be made use of in detecting vanadium. Thus, 2 mg. of vanadium in 5 c. c. of the solution containing excess of salicylamidoxime can be just detected by extraction, at a p_H of 3-4, with 1 c. c. of *isoamyl* alcohol.

Detection of Ti^{IV} with Salicylaldoxime.—As little as 2.47 μ g Ti can be detected by extracting the solution containing excess of the aldoxime, at a p_H of 3.4, with 1 c. c. of chloroform. The optimum p_H for the extraction has been found to be 2.8-7.0.

DISCUSSION

The reactions of salicylamidoxime are comparable to those of the aldoxime (salicylaldoxime), but the p_H values for the incipient precipitation of the metals by the former are somewhat higher. This suggests (cf. Irving and Williams, *Nature*, 1948, 162, 746; Martell and Calvin, "Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds", p. 120, Prentice-Hall, Inc., 1952) that the amidoxime complexes are somewhat less stable than the corresponding aldoxime complexes. A specific influence of the basic $-NH_2$ group in decreasing the strength of the copper specific grouping of the *o*-hydroxy-arylaldoximes is thereby indicated. Since such p_H data are not as yet available for salicylhydroxamic acid, a comparison with this substance is not possible at this stage. From the p_H data reported here, the order of stability of the complexes of some common metals can be expressed as: $Pd^{II} > Cu^{II} > UO_2^{II} > Ni^{II} > Fe^{II} > Co^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II}$. This is more or less the same as that observed, from the p_H data of Flagg and Furman (*loc. cit.*) for the salicylaldoxime complexes.

The p_H of the incipient precipitation, in equimolar solutions, of copper and nickel are more widely different in the case of the amidoxime compared to that for the aldoxime. Furthermore, zinc and cadmium do not form any definite compound with the amidoxime, and their precipitation is prevented altogether in the presence of ammonium chloride. These facts are indicative of a greater selectivity of the amidoxime compared to that of the aldoxime, and thereby furnishes further experimental support to Freiser's view (*Analyst*, 1952, 77, 830) that organic reagents yielding less stable metal chelates are usually more selective than those giving more stable ones. The identification limits for copper, nickel, bismuth and titanium by precipitation and those of uranium, iron and titanium by colour-formation in suitable solvents with salicylamidoxime are comparable to those for the aldoxime. But for the detection of vanadium the amidoxime is much less sensitive than the aldoxime. This is interesting to note in view of the close analogy found so far between the analytical reactions of the two substances.